

An Exquisite Dvitirthi Jaina Image from Odisha Preserved in the British Museum, London

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During the research visit to the British Museum, London in 2022 the author came across a splendid collection of Jaina antiquities which span for about 2000 years. It comprises of stone and bronze artefacts, manuscripts, paintings and textiles of superb aesthetic value. Among this splendid collection the sculpture of our present discourse, that is, the Dvitirthi Jaina image from Odisha is a fascinating one both for its iconographic value and artistic richness. The present paper endeavours to unravel the iconographic details and stylistic features of the Dvitirthi Jaina image housed in the British Museum and ascertain its significance in the art heritage of the Jaina tradition.

Before delving into the image of our present study it is essential to understand the concept of Dvitirthi image in Jaina iconography. In this type of image there is the representation of two Jinas on one slab¹. However it is interesting to note that the reference of such images are hardly mentioned in the Jaina texts. Such images came into existence in the post Gupta period and became popular in central India. However some specimens of Dvitirthi type is also reported from Eastern India of which our present image is from Odisha. The Dvitirthi images usually exhibit three varieties².

- i. Two figures of same Tirthakaras carved on a common slab
- ii. Two figures of different Tirthankaras carved on a common slab without their respective symbols
- iii. Two figures of different Tirthankaras carved on the same slab with symbols of the respective Jinas depicted on the pedestal.

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Since the texts do not mention about Dvitirthi Jaina images the scholars have conjectured that its genesis lies in the innovations on the part of the artists and *acharyas* who probably wanted to carve composite images³ Professor Tiwari suggested the iconographic akinness of Dvitirthi and Tritirthi (representation of three Tirthankaras in one slab) Jaina images to the Brahmanical conception of Trinity where three gods are represented together with their attributes and mounts in a single pedestal. He further opined that the Dvitirthi Jaina images were probably inspired by the Hariharapitamaha images⁴.

It is generally accepted by scholars that the aim of chiseling such images was to worship more than one Tirthankara in one place. In such a conception majority of the Dvitirthi images showcase the representation of the figures of Tirthankara Risabhanatha and Tirthankara Mahavira, that is, the first and the twenty fourth Jina.

Coming to the image of our present study it may be stated that it is undoubtedly one of the most superbly carved Dvitirthi sculpture of the Jaina artistic tradition. The slab on which the image is carved is considered to be a temple fragment from Odisha belonging to 11th century CE of the Eastern Ganga phase⁵. The sculpture is carved in schist and measures 69 cm x 36 cm. It is a significant artefact of the Bridge Collection which was gifted to the Museum in 1872. Presently it is kept under the safe custody of the Asia Department of the Museum with the Accession number G33/ dc57a/ S3.(Plate 1) It is an uninscribed image.

Coming to the iconographic and stylistic characteristic of our image it can be seen here that Tirthankara Rishabhanatha is carved on the left and Tirthankara Mahavira on the right standing elegantly side by side in *kayotsarga* posture. The arms of both the Tirthankaras hang down vertically along the torso touching the thigh with their fingertips. Risabhanatha has a high *jatamukuta* arranged beautifully into spiral curls. A critical observation of Risabhanatha reveals the artistic rendering of the *kesavallari* which falls over his shoulder. On the other hand Tirthankara Mahavira's hair is artistically arranged in curls with a prominent *usnisa*. Both the Tirthankaras have elongated ear lobes and long cylindrical arms reaching down to the knees. Both the figures display proportionate physiognomy. The broad shoulders with narrow waists seen in both the figures accentuate the anatomical charm of the image. The eyes are cast down probably intended to radiate calm peacefulness in the figures. *Sirascakra* without decoration surround the heads of both the Tirthankaras. On the top border of the back slab are tri-linear *cchatras*, *kevala* trees, drum and cymbals played by disembodied hands. The tri-linear *chhatras* are placed above the heads of the Tirthankaras. The tri-linear *chhatras* over the head of Tirthankara Risabhanatha is mutilated. Garland bearing *vidyadhara*s on both sides of

tri- linear *chhatra* are yet another significant feature of this image. Though the Tirthakaras are carved on a common slab, they stand on artistically carved separate lotus pedestal. Both Risabhanatha and Mahavīra are flanked by male *chauri* bearers above the pedestal. Among them two are chiseled on the outer side of the back slab and two at the middle of the Tirthakaras. They stand in *abhanga* posture carrying *chauri* in one hand and display *katyavalambita* posture on the other. The pedestal of the image is very interesting. A couchant bull and a lion, the cognizances of Risabhanatha and Mahavīra are chiseled respectively on the pedestal. The centrally faced lion as the *lanchana* of Mahavīra is again flanked by two crouching lions. A tiny figure of Indra mounted on a elephant is carved beside the bull. Two devotees who can be identified as donor couple are visible on the extreme left of the pedestal.

The exquisite chiseling of our Dvitirthi sculpture probably indicates the religio - stylistic significance of the image .In order to investigate our proposed assumption a study of the image in the geo- religious spacial context may be attempted. In this regard it may be stated that Odisha, the place of provenance of our image, witnessed a continuous history of Jainism from its early days till atleast the medieval period. In Odisha it mostly spread to the North- Western parts of the state, that is, the districts of Balasore, Bhadrak, Keonjhar, Mayurbhanj, Jajpur, Cuttack, Jagatsinghpur, Kendrapara, Khordha, Puri, Boudh, Bolangir in Western Odisha and Koraput and Rayagada in Southern Odisha. Among jaina vestiges some Dvitirthi images have been reported from Odisha. A comparative analysis of the Dvitirthi images of Odisha with our image may be undertaken in order to situate our icon within the atelier of Dvitirthi Jain image from Odisha.

A Dvitirthi Jaina image from Pratap nagari in the district of Cuttack displays remarkable resemblance to our image⁶. Preserved in the Jain Heritage Museum Pratap nagari, the sculpture showcases standing Risabhanatha and Mahavīra in *kayotsarga* posture in one slab but on separate lotus pedestal just like the image of our study. The tri- linear *chhatra*, the garland bearing *vidyadharas*, *chauri* bearers, bull and lion cognizances and presence of donor couples are chiseled like our image. Similarity is also visible in the hairdress of the Tirthankaras, that is, *jatamukuta* for Risabhanatha and curly hair for Mahavīra. In addition to the iconographic similitude, the image exhibits stylistic resemblance indicating a common atelier. (Plate 2)

Another Dvitirthi image with Risabhanatha and Mahavīra on a common slab from Digambara Jain temple, Choudhury Bazar, Cuttack may be taken a note of. Here too Risabhanatha and Mahavīra are carved on a single slab with separate lotus pedestal and bull and lion as the respective Jina's cognizances. The other iconographic similarity with our image

in the British Museum is the presence of the tri- linear *chhatras*, *kevala* tree, flying *vidyadhar*, cymbals played by unembodied hands at the top. Though donors are visible on the pedestal, but they are carved at the middle instead of extreme left as seen in our image. The *chauri* bearers at the middle are carved in profile whereas our British Museum image show frontal position. Another deviation from our image is the presence of decorated back throne with mouldings and triangular fleuron. The image of Risabhanatha shows partial mutilation of the face which prevents us from ascertaining its facial expression. Stylistically this image too shows close linkage to our image. However, the Dvitirthi image of the British Museum collection shows a much-developed sense of refinement and sophistication⁷. (Plate 3)

A Risabhanatha and Mahavīra image from Adyashakti temple, Kantola Athagarh is yet another Jain Dvitirthi image from Odisha. It is in the district of Cuttack. Unfortunately the image is mutilated with the heads of the Tirthankaras missing. However, the carving of the bull and lion as *lanchanas* on the pedestal helps us in identifying the Tirthankara figures as Risabhanatha and Mahavīra. Like our image the Jinas stand on separate lotus pedestal with *chauri* bearers flanking them. *Astagrahas* are chiseled on the sides of the image. This iconographic element is absent in our image preserved in the British Museum. Unfortunately the mutilated condition of the image prevents us from undertaking further icono- stylistic comparative probe⁸.

Another icon of Dvitirthi Jaina conception is found from the temple in Sitalasvara village in Jajpur district of Odisha. Unfortunately, the upper part of the image is broken. From the *lanchanas* on the pedestal it can be surmised that the two Tirthankaras represented on the slab are Mahavīra and Parsvanātha. The Jinas are standing in *kayotsarga* posture. Thus the two Tirthankaras represented in the Jajpur image is different from our British Museum image. In the Jajpur image the defaced image of Parsvanatha is present, but the upper half of the figure of Mahavīra is broken. The pedestal is also differently carved than our image. The pedestal is divided into five segments of which two segments chisel lion and snake, that is, the cognizances of Mahavīra and Parsvanatha. The other segments are decorated with floral patterns. The highly abraded snake canopy over the head of Parsvanatha is extant. A defaced figure is visible on the left side of Parsvanatha. It may be conjectured that the figure possibly represent the *chauri* bearer. Since the image has suffered severe damage, it prevents us from delving into its stylistics. However, from the point of view of iconography the image is quite different from the Dvitirthi image preserved in the British Museum⁹. (Plate 4)

A detailed study of the Dvitirthi Jaina image from Odisha in the British Museum collection undoubtedly resonate to other Dvitirthi images from Odisha both iconographically and stylistically. However, our Dvitirthi image of British Museum collection definitely shows a developed sense of form, linear rhythm and sophistication. Though the date of our image coincides with the Eastern Ganga period, the absence of inscription on the image prevents us from unraveling the issue of origin and authorship, that is, the context of the image. However, the minutely carved iconographic features with refined aesthetics definitely speak of a strong atelier under supervision of which this magnificent artwork was produced. In fact, Jainism in Odisha, besides its religious significance, also contributed greatly to the cultural heritage of the region¹⁰ and our Dvitirthi image bear testimony to this.

Thus, in the concluding reflection it may be undoubtedly stated that the Dvitirthi Jain image from Odisha preserved in the British Museum, London is one of the finest known images of its kind. The well-proportioned physiognomy, iconographic precision, stylistic elegance - all speak of the mastery of the artist in chiseling this exquisite piece. The inward glance and serene expression are fitting artistic touch to the peaceful liberators, that is, the Jinas in this image. This can be considered a masterstroke, a purposeful attempt on the part of the artist to transcend the mere stony physicality of the image to the spiritual quest that the image stood for.

References:

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5. http://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/A_1872-0701-99
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Plates:

**PLATE 1: Dvitirthi Jain Image, Odisha, British Museum, London
(Photo Courtesy: British Museum)**

PLATE 2: Dvitirthi Jaina Image, Jain Heritage Museum,Pratap Nagari, Cuttack District (Photo Courtesy: Ashis Ranjan Sahoo, 2015)

PLATE 3: Dvitirthi Jain Image, Digambar Jain Temple, Choudhury Bazar, Cuttack District (Photo Courtesy: Ashis Ranjan Sahoo, 2015)

**PLATE 4 : Dvitirthi Jaina Image, Sitalesvara, Jajpur District
(Photo Courtesy: Ashis Ranjan Sahoo, 2015)**